

**THE RELEVANCE OF THE METHODS AND TECHNICAL METHODS OF
TEACHING NATIVE LANGUAGE SCIENCE TO STUDENTS IN THE SCHOOLS OF
OUR REPUBLIC TODAY.**

Samarkand regional Bulungur District 57-general secondary education school native
language and literature teacher:

Ubaydullayeva Ramiza Abdullayevna

Annotation: the following cited article deals with the positive aspects and nature of teaching native language science to students. It also highlights the methodology and similar techniques that are important in teaching native language education to today's youth

Keywords: method, education, knowledge, methodology, students, skills, phonetics, potential, conclusion

Main part: the method is actually derived from the Greek word „metodos, which means" knowledge and research is lost", " theory", " doctrine "as M A'nolam i1. M etodica (yurt, "methodike") is the science of M etodes, paths, and means to perform, carry out, perform a work, sum of M etodes, methods, or give a measure of growth methods. The subject of the subject of the methodology of teaching mother tongue in elementary grades is the science of ways and means of teaching students the Uzbek language, mastering the native language, that is, mastering speech, reading and writing, grammar and spelling. The methodology is based on the educational and educational tasks set before the school, determines the tasks of teaching the native language and the M azm flour, checks the educational process, determines the laws of the same process and the scientifically based system of teaching methods. M the science of etodica studies the following issues: 1. Determines the tasks of training and mazm flour. What to train? answers the question, that is, primary classes determine the programs, educational content of the native language course, create textbooks and manual alar for students, improve them, and constantly monitor the relevance and compliance of sam. 2. Teaching methods, principles, methods, lesson and its types, students develop a consistent system of practical work - exercises and written work, that is, "Q anday should be taught?" will prepare an answer to the question. 3. Giving students knowledge of their native language and generating a skill solves issues about the most useful conditions from a scientific point of view, that is, " why should I be taught the same way?" prepares an answer to the question. Studies the most useful materials, m etodes, bases selected m etodes, experimentally checks recommendations.

Although the importance of practical work in the school is properly evaluated by students, they find it difficult to use the theoretical knowledge of students in practice. Little use of grammar rules when performing written work. In fact, transcribing and practical exercises play an important role in order to improve spelling literacy. From psychological studies, it turns out that spelling literacy is formed gradually. Even in the transition from practical to rule, the process of mastering is slow. It is initially discussed orally under the guidance of a teacher. Gradually, students begin to think and meditate and realize. In all writing classes, it is possible to increase their spelling literacy by emphasizing the correct writing rules for students and doing practical work. In all native language classes, students are given time to repeat the previously mentioned lessons in order to improve their knowledge and skills. Repetition helps to identify, take into account and, at the same time, consolidate knowledge. In general secondary schools, new knowledge is given at the same time as the repetition of the previous ones, and little by little in the process of repetition. Through repetition, students organize, strengthen their knowledge.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-3, ISSUE-5

The modern lesson is that a student, a listener, a teacher should not remain a speaker. Perhaps the teacher should become a director who will monitor the lesson and regulate it. The teacher should organize the lesson in such a way that all the student will have an independent opinion on this topic, be able to say his opinion, if there is a drawback, be able to correct it based on the response of his comrades and the teacher. Depending on the character nature of the lesson, the lesson should be achieved in an interactive way. The use of tests and handouts in classes also gives a good result. It is important to rely on the life experience of students when giving knowledge of the native language. The teacher relies on the life experience of children, their practice of speech, both at the stage of collecting evidential materials, for which generalization of a theoretical nature is necessary, and in order to put the knowledge given into practice. As a result of the study of linguistic knowledge, the quality of speech activity of students changes, awareness increases. Connecting language learning with life provides a basis for understanding the materiality of the world. With this, one of the main tasks of native language lessons at the same time, the issue of proper observation in students and the cultivation of the skills to clearly state their thoughts in oral and written form is solved. In this, the teacher is required to pay special attention to the formation of the dialectical thinking skill in students.

When carrying out the education of the mother tii, the psychological and young personality of the students should be taken into account by the educator. It is advisable to use modern multimedia tools more widely. Wider use of pedagogical technologies, taking into account the capabilities and age characteristics of students. Development of large-scale cooperation with linguistic scientists, writers and poets. This is accompanied by increased enthusiasm, respect and, of course, interest in readers in relation to language, culture. Oynaijahon, issues such as the preparation of materials in the native language and literary language were considered as important as possible, so that the manna in the means of Mass Communication did not make shallow materials available to the public.

Conclusion: the points presented determine the methodology for teaching the native language to schoolchildren, taking into account the internal connection between objects. 1. Taking into account that all (lexical, phonetic, word-making, grammatical) aspects of language are interconnected and each of them has its own characteristics, it is necessary for students to master the features of each side of the language and the connection between them so that they can consciously master the language. The system of learning the native language, taking into account the peculiarity of age, is drawn up taking into account the essence of phonetics, lexicology, word making and the interconnection of grammar. This case is taken into account both in determining the procedure for studying program materials and in determining the content of education (the inextricable connection between program departments). 2. The influence of all aspects of language on each other is manifested in its function as a weapon of communication. For the purpose of communication as the basic unit of language, it is necessary to correctly pronounce or write a word, to be equally understandable to all those who speak the same language, to be grammatically correctly structured in a sentence. Taking this into account, in order for younger readers to understand the essence of the pronunciation of the language, graphic, lexical, word making and the interconnection of grammatical sides, the task of language communication is taken into account when studying the program material, that is, the joint use of all sides of the language in the process of communication with people. To this end, in the study of the phonetic side of the language, great

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-3, ISSUE-5

importance is placed on explaining the meaning and pronunciation of the word forming unity, the position of the sound in distinguishing the meaning of the word.

Reference:

1. Normatov U. "Ona tili o'qitishning dolzrb muammolari", -T.: 2008 y
2. https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ona_tili
3. <https://kun.uz/uz/35715601>
4. ona tili fanini o'quchilarga o'rgatishning ahamiyati va xususiyati
T.N.Butayorovna
5. [Ona tili o'qitish metodikasi \(K.Qopsimova, S.Matchonov va b.\).pdf](#)

